

Investigation of the Reaction of Fluorine containing 1,3-Dihydro-3-(1,5-dihydro-3-methyl-5-oxo-1-phenyl-4*H*-pyrazol-4-ylidene)-2*H*-indol-2-one with Hydrazine Derivatives

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The reaction of 1,3-dihydro-3-(1,5-dihydro-3-methyl-5-oxo-1-phenyl-4*H*-pyrazol-4-ylidene)-2*H*-indol-2-ones (**3a-d**) with various hydrazines has been studied in the absolute ethanol/glacial acetic acid medium. Reaction of **3a-c** with phenyl hydrazine in absolute ethanol gave exclusively spiro compounds (64-76%), while in glacial acetic acid, a mixture of spiro compound (18-67%), hydrazones (14-25%) and a condensed compound (22-33%) was formed. **3** however gave only two compounds. Analogous reaction of **3a,c** with hydrazine hydrate in absolute ethanol furnished a mixture of spiro (36-41%) and condensed derivative (22-26%). The compounds were characterised by elemental analyses, ir, pmr, ¹⁹F nmr and mass spectral data.

Continuing our interest in the synthesis of biodynamic spiro indole derivatives¹⁻⁵ and the reactions of α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds with hydrazine derivatives⁶⁻¹⁰, we now report studies on the reactions of 1,3-dihydro-3-(1,5-dihydro-3-methyl-5-oxo-1-phenyl-4*H*-pyrazol-4-ylidene)-2*H*-indol-2-ones (**3**) with phenylhydrazine and hydrazine hydrate. Pyrazol(4-ylidene)-2*H*-indol-2-ones (**3a-d**) with appropriate fluorine substituents, were synthesised exclusively by Knoevenagel reaction of fluorinated indol-2,3-diones (**1**) with 2,4-dihydro-5-methyl-2-phenyl-3*H*-pyrazol-3-one (1 : 1 ratio) in absolute ethanol.

A literature survey reveals some controversial results during reactions of 1,3-dihydro-3-(2-phenyl-2-oxoethylidene)-2*H*-indol-2-ones with hydrazine derivatives^{11,12}. Rather surprisingly, the title reaction with **3** has not been studied so far.

The cycloaddition reactions of **3** seem to be quite interesting because in addition to α,β -unsaturated carbonyl systems in the side-chain, an amidic carbonyl group can also interact. Moreover, no attention has been given so far

to such possibilities in the reactions of oxindolidene with various amino derivatives^{13,14}, although such reactions with various enamines have been studied. This is the first report of the exclusive synthesis of 1,3-dihydro-3-(1,5-dihydro-3-methyl-5-oxo-1-phenyl-4*H*-pyrazol-4-ylidene)-2*H*-indol-2-ones (**3a-d**) and the reaction of **3a-d** with phenylhydrazine and hydrazine hydrate in absolute ethanol/glacial acetic acid.

Reaction of **3** with phenyl hydrazine in absolute ethanol resulted in the exclusive formation of spiro compound (**4**; 64-76%). In glacial acetic acid, however, it resulted in the formation of a mixture of spiro compound (**4**; 18-67%), hydrazones (**5**; 14-25%) and condensed compound (**6**; 22-33%). In the case of **3d** ($R^1 = \text{COCH}_3$), only two compounds (spiro **4d**; 48%) and hydrazones (**5d**; 22%) were obtained.

Analogous reactions of **3a,c** with hydrazine hydrate in absolute ethanol, furnished a mixture of spiro derivative (**4e,f**; 36-41%) and condensed systems (**6e,f** 22-26%).

Results and Discussion

The reaction of **3a-c** with phenylhydrazine in absolute ethanol gave a single product which showed characteristic ir absorption bands at 3 360 (NH), 1 660 (C=O), 1 630 cm^{-1} (C=N) and ^1H nmr signals at δ 1.47 (3H, s, CH_3), 6.43 (1H, br, CH), 6.85–7.82 (13H, m, ArH) and 11.52 (1H, br, NH). Further, in the mass spectrum of **4c**, the molecular ion peak (M^+) was observed at m/z 411 (21%) corresponding exactly to its molecular weight, and other characteristic mass fragments were observed at 278 ($M^+ - \text{C}_6\text{H}_9\text{N}_2$) (100%), 201 ($278 - \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$) (35.5%) and 173 ($201 - \text{N}_2$).

On the basis of the presence of CH proton signal in ^1H nmr and C=O absorption in ir spectra, the product has been identified as spiro[indole-pyrazolo(3,4-c)pyrazol] derivative instead of a hydrazone or pyrazolopyridazinoindole system. An analogous reaction of **3c** with phenylhydrazine in glacial acetic acid medium gave three products which were separated by column chromatography. The first compound obtained from petroleum ether : benzene (9 : 1) fraction showed characteristic ir bands at 3 380–3 320 (NH), 1 670 (C=O) and 1 620 cm^{-1} (C=N) and ^1H nmr signals at δ 1.61 (3H, s, CH_3), 7.28–8.082 (13H, m, ArH), 11.86 (1H, br, NH) ppm. On the basis of the absence of CH proton along with presence of C=O absorption in ir spectrum the compound has been identified as 1,3-dihydro-3-[3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-phenylhydrazono-4H-pyrazol-4-ylidene]-2H-indol-2-one. The proposed structure is supported by its mass spectrum in which the molecular ion peak (M^+) was observed at m/z 411 (10.5%) and other characteristic peaks at 320 ($M^+ - \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N}$) (50.4%), 173 ($320 - \text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{N}_3$) (100%), 77 (C_6H_5)⁺.

The second compound was obtained from petroleum ether : benzene (1 : 1) fraction as a yellow solid (24%). It was characterised as spiro-[3H-indol-3,3'-[3H]pyrazole-(3,4-c)pyrazol]-2(1H)-one (**4c**) on the basis of comparison of spectral and elemental data with the product which was

obtained exclusively in the reaction of **3c** with phenyl hydrazine in alcohol media.

The ethyl acetate : methanol (3 : 1) fraction afforded an orange solid (33%) which showed no C=O and NH absorptions in ir spectrum and its ^1H nmr spectrum showed a singlet at δ 1.32 corresponding to one methyl group alongwith aromatic protons at δ 7.23–8.29. In the mass spectrum, molecular ion peak was observed at m/z 393 (11.2%). The compound has thus been identified as pyrazolo[3',4' 5,6]pyridazino[3,4-b]indole.

An interesting feature was observed when **3d** was treated with $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHNH}_2$ in glacial acetic acid. In this case, only two products were obtained, identified as spiro (48%) and hydrazone derivative (22%) on the basis of spectral and elemental analyses. However, pyrazole-pyridazinoindole derivative could not be formed in this case due to lack of the possibility of enolisation.

When the reaction of **3c** with hydrazine hydrate was carried out in alcohol media, the product was found to be a mixture of spiro and condensed derivative unlike the earlier reaction of **3c** with PhNHNH_2 in alcohol which gave only a spiro compound. The yellow coloured product (36%) showed characteristic ir bands at 3 380–3 100 (NH), 1 670 (C=O), 1 620 cm^{-1} (C=N) and ^1H nmr signals at δ 1.57 (3H, s, CH_3), 7.28–7.77 (m, ArH), 11.92 (1H, s, NH) and 12.73 (1H, s, NH) ppm. Further, in the mass spectrum, the molecular ion peak (M^+) was observed at m/z 335 (68.5%) with other peak at 320 ($M^+ - \text{CH}_3$)

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS **3a-d**

Compd no	R'	X	M p °C	Yield %	N% Found/ (Calcd)
3a	H	H	218	75	13.97 (13.86)
b	H	5F	252	65	13.26 (13.08)
c	H	6F	234	70	12.86 (13.08)
d	COCH ₃	H	226	68	12.80 (12.96)

(41.9%), 188 (M^+ - $C_7H_7N_4$) (100%) and 91 (C_6H_5N) (72.5%). On the basis of presence of CH signal in 1H nmr and C=O absorption in ir spectrum, the compound has been identified as spiro[indole-pyrazole(3,4-*c*)-pyrazol] derivative.

The second compound showed no C=O absorption in ir spectrum. 1H nmr spectrum displayed aromatic region signal at δ 6.9–8.17 and NH at δ 11.79 ppm. In the mass spectrum, molecular ion peak (M^+) was observed at 317 (11.8%). On the basis of these spectral data, the product has been identified as pyrazole[3',4': 5,6]pyridazino [3,4-*b*]-indole.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 557 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra ($CDCl_3$ or $DMSO-d_6$) on a JEOL FX 90Q MHz instrument using TMS as internal standard and mass spectra on a MS-30 or MS-50 Kratos mass spectrometer at 70 eV.

1,3-Dihydro-3-(2-methyl-5-oxo-1-phenyl-4H-pyrazol-4-ylidene)-2H-indol-2-one (3): A mixture of appropriate isatin (**1**; 0.01 mol) and pyrazolone (**2**; 0.01 mol) in absolute ethanol (35 ml) was refluxed for 3.5–4.0 h. On cooling, a grey coloured solid mass was separated which was recrystallised from benzene to give violet coloured crystals. The other compounds (**3b–d**) were synthesised similarly (Table 1).

Reaction of 3c with phenyl hydrazine (in alcohol): Spiro[3*H*-indol-3,3'-(3*H*)-pyrazolo(3,4-*c*)pyrazol]-2-(1*H*)-one was synthesised by refluxing a mixture of **3c** (0.01 mol) and phenylhydrazine (0.012 mol) in absolute ethanol for 5 h. On cooling, the separated yellow compound was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

Reaction of 3c with phenylhydrazine (in glacial acetic acid): A mixture of **3c** (0.01 mol) and $C_6H_5NHNH_2$ (0.01 mol) in glacial acetic acid (40 ml) was refluxed for 10 h. The progress of reaction was checked by tlc. On completion of the reaction, the mixture was concentrated

Scheme 1

TABLE 2—YIELDS OF PRODUCTS FROM THE REACTION OF 3 WITH HYDRAZINE AND PHENYLHYDRAZINE

Compd no	Reactant	Solvent	Yield of products (%)		
			4	5	6
3a	$C_6H_5NHNH_2$	C_2H_5OH	64	—	—
3a	$C_6H_5NHNH_2$	CH_3COOH	18	25	28
3b	$C_6H_5NHNH_2$	C_2H_5OH	72	—	—
3b	$C_6H_5NHNH_2$	CH_3COOH	67	14	22
3c	$C_6H_5NHNH_2$	C_2H_5OH	76	—	—
3c	$C_6H_5NHNH_2$	CH_3COOH	38	24	33
3d	$C_6H_5NHNH_2$	CH_3COOH	48	22	—
3a	NH_2NH_2	C_2H_5OH	41	—	22
3c	NH_2NH_2	C_2H_5OH	36	—	26

TABLE 3—ANALYTICAL DATA OF SPIRO COMPOUNDS (4)

Compd no.*	R^1	X	R^2	Mp $^{\circ}C$	Colour	N% Found/ (Calcd.)
4a ^a	H	H	C_6H_5	140	Cremish yellow	17.68 (17.80)
b ^b	H	5F	C_6H_5	290d	Yellow	17.14 (17.02)
c ^a	H	6F	C_6H_5	205	Light yellow	17.01 (17.02)
d ^b	$COCH_3$	H	C_6H_5	162	Orange	16.14 (16.08)
e	H	H	H	196	Greenish yellow	21.98 (22.07)
f	H	6F	H	222	Greenish yellow	20.72 (20.88)

*Column fraction: petroleum ether–benzene, ratio, ^a1:1 and ^b1:3.

TABLE 4—ANALYTICAL DATA OF HYDRAZONES AND CONDENSED COMPOUNDS (5, 6)

Compd no.*	R ¹	X	R ²	M.p. °C	Colour	N% : Found/ (Calcd.)
5a ^a	H	H	C ₆ H ₅	210	Yellow	17.68 (17.80)
b ^b	H	5F	C ₆ H ₅	240	Yellow	17.16 (17.02)
c ^c	H	6F	C ₆ H ₅	282	Dark yellow	17.06 (17.02)
d ^d	COCH ₃	H	C ₆ H ₅	130	Orange yellow	15.56 (15.82)
6a ^e	—	H	C ₆ H ₅	175	Dark yellow	18.42 (18.65)
b ^e	—	5F	C ₆ H ₅	200d	Orange	17.72 (17.80)
c ^f	—	6F	C ₆ H ₅	>195	Orange	17.72 (17.80)
e	—	H	H	242	Green	22.96 (23.99)
f	—	6F	H	>320	Dark green	22.12 (22.07)

Column fraction : ^apetroleum ether, ^bpetroleum ether-benzene (8 : 2), ^cpetroleum ether-benzene (9 : 1), ^dpetroleum ether-benzene (4 : 1), ^ebenzenc-ethyl acetate (1 : 1), ^fbenzenc-ethyl acetate (1 : 3).

and poured into ice-water. The resulting solid was filtered and gave three spots on tlc. The three components were separated by column chromatography over silica gel using petroleum ether, benzene, ethyl acetate and methanol in different polarity ratios as eluants, and characterised (Tables 2 and 3) as (a) 5-phenylhydrazone-1-phenyl-4H-pyrazol-1-ylidene-2H-indol-2-one, (b) spiro-[3H-indol-3,3'-(3H)-pyrazole[3,4-c]pyrazol-2(1H)-one and (c) pyrazolo[3',4' : 5,6]pyridazino[3,4-b]indole.

Reaction of 3c with hydrazine hydrate : A mixture of 3c (0.01 mol) and NH₂.NH₂.H₂O (0.012 mol) in absolute ethanol was refluxed for 6 h. The reaction mixture was then concentrated and poured into ice-water. The resulting solid was dried and crystallised from chloroform. The filtrate was concentrated and kept for 3–4 days when grey coloured crystals appeared. These were filtered and recrystallised from methanol and characterised as a spiro (4f) and condensed (6f) derivative.

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